

Low Latency of Comparator Design using Quantum Dot Cellular Automata

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ABSTRACT

Logic gates and QCA wires can be implemented by Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA). In this paper, one bit, four bit and eight-bit comparators are designed based on QCA. QCA Designer is used to simulate the circuits. The results show that the proposed comparators are of correct logic function. Analysis shows that the latency of proposed circuits does not increase linearly with bit size. Hence the proposed circuit has good delay property. The QCA based designs have been validated and subjected to simulation using the QCA Designer tool ver. 2.0.3.

Keywords: QCA, Comparator, combinational logic circuits

1. INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor fabrication technology has changed quickly in the last decades, but some applications require less power and more speed [1]. These problems motivate scientists to find an alternative technology as a solution. Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA) is one of the candidate technologies in this field [2]. It is a new nanotechnology that enables low power, high density, and a high-speed structure to design any digital function at a nano-scale [3]. QCA is a technique that can be used to create reliable computer systems in the future. Lent et al. presented the first quantum dot model in the early 1990s. No current conveys information from one cell to another using a polarization state, and all operations rely on quantum phenomena.

Unlike standard electronics, logic conditions are triggered by a cell rather than voltage levels, which is unique. The machine will use a two-electron arrangement to process data. Manufacturing insufficiency and improper structure are essential factors in circuit quality. In QCA, information was sent via clocking technology [4-5]. Much research on QCA-based circuits has been done due to these characteristics. Adders, multipliers, memories, multiplexers, and other digital circuits have been designed using this technique. In CMOS technology, a comparator comprises a specialized high-gain differential amplifier. It has two input terminals and one binary digital output. They're ubiquitous in devices like successive approximation ADCs and relaxation oscillators that

measure and digitize analog signals [6]. Different components, including diodes, transistors, and op-amps, can create such devices. They are used to drive logic circuits in various electrical devices. But, in QCA technology, a comparator circuit has 3 3-input majority gates, inverter gates, and cells. This paper presents a comparator circuit designed by QCA nanotechnology. When two voltages are compared, a comparator circuit produces a '1' (the voltage on the positive side; VDD in the example) or a '0' (the voltage on the negative side) to indicate which is bigger. Comparators are often employed to confirm if an input has reached the desired value or not. They play an essential role in digital circuits like microcontrollers in QCA technology [7-9]. As a result, high-performance comparator circuits have gotten much attention, and effort has gone into improving the performance of QCA comparator circuits. This research focuses on efficient multi-layer comparator circuit design using inverter and majority gates to form the foundation of the comparator design. Because of cell and area consumption restrictions in relevant research, the research presents an efficient QCA-based comparator design to solve these shortcomings. This design uses three layers of 90-degree cells in a 0.04 μm^2 layout to eliminate coplanar crossovers and ensure accessible inputs and outputs. The three-layer arrangement and lack of coplanar crossovers are a novel approach to ensuring accessible inputs and outputs, which contributes to the design's overall efficiency. Furthermore, leveraging QCA's clocking technique for computational pipelining and signal flow management is new, as it allows the comparator to generate output across three clock phases. QCA Designer-E is used to assess practical accuracy, cost, and power, showing that the suggested design is substantially more efficient in terms of cell and area usage than earlier designs.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The fundamentals of the QCA nanotechnology, digital comparator circuit, and existing related works are presented in Section 2. The proposed QCA-based comparator circuit is detailed in Section 3. Section 4 presents the simulation results and comparison evaluation.

2. BASICS OF QCA:

Quantum-dot cellular automata (QCA) nanotechnology is an effective methodology and

possibly the best replacement for CMOS technology. It offers many advantages such as area efficiency, high speed, low-power dissipation, and scalability in the ultra-nanoscale region compared with the CMOS technology [10]. The operation of QCA-based circuits does not require a transistor, thus, external voltage is not required. Therefore, the QCA technology has become popular and valuable in the current systems. The present work proposes an area-efficient digital comparator circuit. The proposed comparator uses fewer QCA cells and clock phases than the existing similar designs. The energy dissipation of the proposed design is also investigated to improve energy efficiency.

The fundamental of the QCA nanotechnology starts with the QCA cell. Four quantum dots exist in a QCA cell in which two electrons stay in the opposite corners due to a Columbic repulsion force. The positions of these two electrons in the cell affect the logic formation for digital applications. The specific location of the electron pair in the cell generates a unique polarization value. Hence, polarization values of +1 and -1 in a cell are possible, which create both true and false logic, respectively. The Boolean logic representation of the QCA cell is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Cell Illustration of A) Unpolarized cell B) Polarized Logic 1 c) polarized Logic 0

QCA wire is an important element in QCA circuits. The QCA wire causes movement of data in the QCA circuit via cell-to-cell interactions. Figure 2 shows a QCA wire that uses different clock phases. The data in the QCA wires move in a specific manner. The data flow from Phase 0 to Phase 1, Phase 1 to Phase 2, Phase 2 to Phase 3, Phase 3 to Phase 0, and so on by following the same path in the QCA wire.

Fig 2: QCA based wire using different clock phases

The various methodologies such as planar and multilayer are adopted for the QCA designs to cross and pass the logic. The QCA cell contains two types of cells based on the quantum-dot locations. The QCA cell is further classified as regular or 90° and rotated or 45° cells. Therefore, two methods are available for the planar crossing of the wires. The first planar method is the combination of regular and rotated cells at the crossing point. The second planar method is based on the QCA-clock phases, which is also known as logical crossover. The other crossing methodology is a multilayer process in which a minimum of three layers are used for effective crossing of the wires.

3. PROPOSED WORK:

Comparator is a module where two numbers are compared. It is a combinational logic circuit and widely used in the core of microprocessor units. It has two inputs (A and B) and three outputs [A less than B (A_L_B), A equal to B (A_E_B), and A greater than B (A_G_B)]. The comparator outputs show the comparative relationship of the numbers. Comparison of the input numbers is performed for the less than (L), equal (E), and greater than (G) operations, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3: Block Diagram of a Comparator

Three possibilities can occur in case of a two-number comparison. If the A_L_B condition is fulfilled, then the A_L_B output will be at logic high, whereas the A_E_B and A_G_B outputs will be at logic low. Similarly, in the A_E_B and A_G_B operations, the corresponding output will be at logic high. Therefore, one output will be at logic high while the other outputs will be at logic low at any given time. The truth table for the digital comparator circuit is listed in Table

A	B	A_L_B	A_E_B	A_G_B
0	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	0	1
1	1	0	1	0

A digital comparator circuit can be designed using NOT, AND, and XNOR operations, Equation expresses the NOR logic of the A_L_B and A_G_B outputs to obtain the XNOR logic. Here, the NOR logic is generated with the help of the NOT and AND logic, as provided. Hence, the proposed comparator circuit is designed using three AND and four NOT logic.

The schematic view shown in Figure 4 serves as the basis for the proposed digital comparator circuit. The proposed circuit is implemented in such a manner that a minimum number of QCA cells and clock phases are required. The XNOR logic is implemented using the inverted input AND logic. The proposed QCA-based comparator circuit is shown in Figure 4. The proposed layout is verified using the QCA Designer-E tool for a bistable approximation engine. The assumed cell size is 18 nm × 18 nm. The design is constructed using 19 QCA cells and two clock phases only.

Fig 4: Proposed comparator circuit in QCA Designer E

4 SIMULATION RESULTS:

Fig: 5 4*1 Multiplexer circuit using QCA

Fig 6: Simulation output waveform of 4*1 Multiplexer circuit

Fig: Proposed 2-Bit Comparator Circuit using QCA

Fig: 1-Bit comparator circuit using QCA

Fig: Simulation output waveform of proposed 2-bit comparator

Fig: Simulation output waveform of 1-Bit comparator circuit

From the simulated waveforms of various combinational logic circuits such as one bit adder, 1*2 demultiplexer, 4*1 multiplexer, one bit and two-bit comparator circuits are observed. And the performance metrics such as cell count, Latency and Average and total energy dissipation values are calculated. The following table shows the comparative analysis between multiplexer, demultiplexer and comparator circuits.

Circuit Name	Cell Count	Area (nm ²)	Latency	Average Energy Dissipation (eV)	Total Energy Dissipation (eV)
1-bit adder	13	4212	0.25	0.181	0.147
1:2 demultiplexer	11	3564	0.25	0.045	0.124
1:4 demultiplexer	66	21384	0.75	0.329	0.721
2:1 Multiplexer	27	8748	0.75	0.059	0.175
4:1 Multiplexer	79	25596	1.00	0.111	0.331
1-bit comparator	30	9720	0.50	0.086	0.258
2-bit comparator (existing)	200	64800	1.25	0.401	1.197
2-bit comparator (proposed)	113	36612	1.75	0.239	0.715

5. CONCLUSION:

CMOS technology will reach saturation in future ICs due to further scaling issues. QCA nanotechnology is an emerging design methodology with the capability of replacing the CMOS technology. Comparison is a key operation in the processing units of computers. This paper proposes a single-layer low-complexity

QCA-based digital comparator circuit. The proposed comparator circuit is compared with existing similar designs based on the QCA cells, used clock, cell area, covered area, layout cost, and nature of the layer. The proposed comparator outperforms the existing comparators. Energy dissipation using the QCA Designer-E is measured and compared with that of the available designs. Power maps are also presented for the

proposed comparator circuit. The simulation analysis of the proposed comparator circuit demonstrates its importance in the ultra-nanoscale region. The proposed digital comparator is 83.33%, it reduces the number of cells by 24% and improves the energy dissipation is 71.5% with the previous designs.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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